

MPowerBIO

eM-POWERing SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death

Exploitation and Sustainability Plan I

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3	24/04/2021	Final version incorporating partners' comments	I. Delioglani (QPL)
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MPOWERBIO PARTNERS				
Participant No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country	Organisation type
1	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark http://foodbiocluster.dk/	FBCD	DK	Non-profit SME/Cluster
2	TechTour Global https://www.techtour.com/	TTG	BG	SME
3	CLIB https://www.clib-cluster.de/	CLIB	DE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
4	Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/	CTA	ES	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
5	Italbiotec https://www.italbiotec.it/	IBT	IT	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
6	Foodscale Hub https://foodscalehub.com/	FSH	RS	Non-profit Association /Cluster
7	EIT Food https://www.eitfood.eu/	EIT	BE	Non-profit Association
8	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/	IBF	IE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
9	Q-Plan International https://qplan-intl.gr/	QPL	GR	SME
10	Sustainable Innovations Europe https://www.sustainableinnovations.eu/	SIE	ES	SME

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1. Introduction

MPowerBIO is a 30-month project (May 2020 to October 2022) receiving funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

MPowerBIO aims to set up and implement a **capacity building programme for 90 SME clusters** along with an integrated **business support programme for 350 selected SMEs** from their networks, empowering clusters to raise awareness and improve the investment readiness and pitching skills of their SMEs. It will also **build links with investors and connect investment-ready SMEs** identified and supported at regional competitions directly with expert coaches, investors and business partners. A Final Event is envisaged to give regionally selected projects the opportunity to pitch their investment in front of investors and create partnering opportunities.

Moreover, MPowerBIO will **map investment sources and requirements** at EU, national and regional levels with a special focus on the local landscape of the clusters while at the same time complementing any information gaps with interviews of experts and practitioners in the field.

In parallel, the consortium will work closely with the SME clusters to determine their current knowledge and skills in terms of effectively engaging with investors and supporting SMEs to **improve the scalability and investment readiness of their bio-based industry projects** as well as to seek and secure suitable financial opportunities. The consortium will **define the training needs** that will be addressed via a capacity building programme in order to overcome any knowledge and skill gaps that may impede clusters to successfully deliver the MPowerBIO **business support programme** to their SME members.

Finally, to support the investment readiness level assessment and deliver both the capacity building and business support programmes, the project will develop and deploy a dedicated digital platform and tools available to all engaged Clusters and SMEs.

This report aims to outline the Actionable Knowledge that will emerge from the Transition2BIO activities with a view to maximising the impact of the project and systematically plan for its exploitation beyond its lifetime. It provides an overview of:

- the main exploitable assets and their estimated availability date (WHAT);
- the specific target groups that could benefit from them (WHO);
- the potential exploitation routes of those assets (HOW/WHAT FOR).

Remark: *This report has been prepared at the initial phase of the project and constitutes the first version of the “Exploitation and sustainability plan”. It is based on the information provided in the Description of the Action and the project progress until M12 (April 2021). The list of the MPowerBIO exploitation assets will be revised throughout the project implementation and their potential exploitation routes, as well as their innovation potential, will be updated to better address the support needs of the targeted stakeholders. The final and more detailed version of the Plan will be prepared at the end of the project (in M30 – October 2022).*

2. Overview of exploitable assets

The table below presents the MPowerBIO assets and highlights the deliverables and Work Packages they refer to, as well as the partner overall responsible for them.

Table 1 List of MPowerBIO assets

	Title	Related WP/Task	Related deliverable(s)	Partner responsible*
1	Inventory of existing investment sources and respective requirements	T1.1	D1.1	Q-PLAN
2	Skills Gap and Training Needs Analysis	T1.2	D1.2	Q-PLAN
3	Capacity Building Programme for SME clusters	T1.4	D1.5	FSH
4	Business Support Programme for SMEs	T1.4	D1.4	FSH
5	MPowerBIO online platform	T2.1	D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4	TTG
6	Wider network of synergies	T3.1, T3.3	D3.1, D3.2, D3.4	CTA
7	Trained corps of qualified cluster managers	T3.2	D3.3, D3.4	All
8	Networks of investors	T5.2	D5.3, D5.4	All

* The partner leading the consortium effort, while all other partners will contribute to asset development and validation.

Table 2 below features a mapping of the various project assets and the stakeholders that can benefit from each one of them.

Table 2 Mapping of MPowerBIO assets and potential beneficiaries

	Title	Bioeconomy clusters <i>(in the field of bioeconomy)</i>	Related clusters <i>(in the respective national ecosystems)</i>	SMEs	Support Organisations			Investors	Policy makers
					Cluster support	Business support	Innovation support		
1	Inventory of existing investment sources and respective requirements	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
2	Skills Gap and Training Needs Analysis	X	X		X	X	X		X
3	Capacity Building Programme for SME clusters	X	X		X	X	X		X
4	Business Support Programme for SMEs	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
5	MPowerBIO online platform	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
6	Wider network of synergies	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
7	Trained corps of qualified cluster managers			X				X	
8	Networks of investors	X	X	X	X	X	X		

2.1 Inventory of existing investment sources and respective requirements

Description	<p>An inventory of existing investment sources and their respective requirements when it comes to SMEs operating in the bio-based sector. The sources include both public funding programmes and private financing sourcing (e.g., Business Angels, Venture Capitals, Banks, Corporate Investors, etc.), at the European and national levels.</p> <p>The content of the inventory was initially collected by means of a desk research focusing on diverse relevant online sources, including policy documents, white papers, study reports, funding programmes' factsheets, investors' websites, etc., at the regional, national and European levels. However, since data on regional investors is sometimes hard to find, the desk research was rounded off with interviews that were conducted with representatives of financial instruments and investors at national level to highlight their perspectives on investing in innovative SMEs of the bioeconomy sector.</p>																											
Task(s)	T1.1																											
Linked deliverables	D1.1																											
Partner(s) responsible	<p>All partners were involved in the analysis, each one focusing on their own country's investment landscape:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>FBCD</th> <th>TTG</th> <th>CLIB</th> <th>CTA</th> <th>FSH</th> <th>IBT</th> <th>IBF</th> <th>QPL</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>EU landscape</td> <td></td> <td>Private financial resources</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Public funding programmes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>National landscape</td> <td>DK</td> <td>BG, BE</td> <td>DE, AT, NL</td> <td>ES</td> <td>RS</td> <td>IT</td> <td>IE</td> <td>GR</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		FBCD	TTG	CLIB	CTA	FSH	IBT	IBF	QPL	EU landscape		Private financial resources						Public funding programmes	National landscape	DK	BG, BE	DE, AT, NL	ES	RS	IT	IE	GR
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National landscape	DK	BG, BE	DE, AT, NL	ES	RS	IT	IE	GR																				
Exploitation potential	The inventory served the development of the Capacity Building Programme for SME clusters, and the corresponding Business Support Programme aiming to bioeconomy SMEs.																											
Availability	The report was prepared in autumn 2020 and constitutes a confidential document.																											

2.2 Skills Gap and Training Needs Analysis

Description	<p>An analysis that studies the available and missing skills of trainers in SME clusters, exploring two main aspects, namely the trainers' skill level to (i) train the clusters' SMEs that are developing innovative bio-based technologies, products and/or services to improve their investment readiness, as well as (ii) identify, prepare for and engage with suitable investors. The goal was to identify and compare the required set of skills ("<i>to-be condition</i>") against the currently available skill-set ("<i>as-is condition</i>"), based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative research tools, including:</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the review of relevant documentation at regional, national and EU levels to build a framework of the skills required to deliver well-tailored investment readiness services; • semi-structured interviews with expert trainers in clusters, accelerators, innovation agencies, consultancies, as well as prospective trainees from SMEs to cross-reference findings and reveal disparity points that may require further investigation; and • a pan-European online survey addressed to a broader group of trainers in SME clusters across Europe, driving a statistical and econometric analysis, using well-known tools such as regression analysis to highlight important training needs of the cluster trainers in terms of anticipated modules and curriculum.
Task(s)	T1.2
Linked deliverables	D1.2
Partner(s) responsible	Q-PLAN was responsible for the analysis
Exploitation potential	<p>The analysis reveals meaningful insights, conclusions and suggestions, identifying deficit patterns. The collected data are to be imported into a matrix plotting clusters to the identified critical skills, to assess their particular training needs and set the premises for the design of the MPowerBIO capacity building programme.</p> <p>It can also be used as a guide and/or a reference point by all other clusters and companies of the bio-based and agricultural sectors.</p>
Availability	The Skills Gap and Training Needs Analysis is already publicly available through the project's web portal (https://mpowerbio.eu/resources).

2.3 Capacity Building Programme for SME clusters

Description	<p>The Capacity Building Programme offers practical help on how cluster representatives engaged in business support (i.e., managers for strategic decisions) from the bio-based sector and other innovation intermediaries (e.g. innovation agencies, tech transfer hubs, chambers of commerce) can mobilize—and enhance—their skills, resources, services to support SMEs in business development and access to finance. It aims to provide cluster representatives with the rationale to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • assess the investment readiness level (IRL) of their SME members and identify the gaps to achieve high IRL, • review the business model of an SME and build a credible investment use case, • select the right investors, • help SMEs to pitch and manage investor relations, and • advise them on financial strategy and planning <p>The Programme intends to provide:</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • interactive lectures with a team of international professionals from the MPowerBIO consortium; • hands-on tools & techniques with relevant exercises; • learning kits from each session that will allow participants to dive deeper into the topic; • real-life business examples such as best practices and case studies to ensure relevancy; • continuous support & services which will be at the participants' disposal not only during but also after the programme finalisation. <p>The specific topics to be covered under the CBP are:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Training topic and description</th> <th>Partner responsible</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Overview of MPowerBIO SME assessment tools from WP2</td> <td>TTG</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Transversal Competencies and Skills</td> <td>QPLAN</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Understanding the needs of your member</td> <td>QPLAN</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mapping innovation using Technology Readiness levels</td> <td>ITALBIOTEC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Planning for future growth: understanding market trends in bio-based value chains</td> <td>ITALBIOTEC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Break-even analysis: How long does it take for bio-based SMEs to be profitable?</td> <td>FSH</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Finding a product-market fit</td> <td>SIE</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Demystifying the funding landscape - sources of investment for biobased SMEs</td> <td>FSH, IBF</td> </tr> <tr> <td>EIT Food Innovation Model and fostering collaboration across the entire food system</td> <td>EIT FOOD</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Internationalization and access to finance: the power of SME networks</td> <td>FSH</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Training topic and description	Partner responsible	Overview of MPowerBIO SME assessment tools from WP2	TTG	Transversal Competencies and Skills	QPLAN	Understanding the needs of your member	QPLAN	Mapping innovation using Technology Readiness levels	ITALBIOTEC	Planning for future growth: understanding market trends in bio-based value chains	ITALBIOTEC	Break-even analysis: How long does it take for bio-based SMEs to be profitable?	FSH	Finding a product-market fit	SIE	Demystifying the funding landscape - sources of investment for biobased SMEs	FSH, IBF	EIT Food Innovation Model and fostering collaboration across the entire food system	EIT FOOD	Internationalization and access to finance: the power of SME networks	FSH
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Task(s)	T1.4, T3.2																						
Linked deliverables	D1.5, D3.3, D3.4																						
Partner(s) responsible	FSH is responsible for the overall design and setup of the programme, whereas CLIB is responsible for the supervision of the delivery of CBP trainings. All project partners contributed to the Programme delivery by allocating their experts to prepare and deliver at least one training session under the CBP (see the table above).																						
Exploitation potential	<p>The Capacity Building Programme will allow designated cluster trainers to mobilise and enhance their skills, resources and services to support SMEs in business development and access to finance, helping them cross the 'valley of death' stage.</p> <p>The different training materials (recordings of live webinars, presentations, additional material) will be available on the MPowerBIO e-learning platform (https://mpowerbio.eu/) to the Associated SME clusters as a guide and/or reference point and for further training ambitions.</p>																						
Availability	The Capacity Building Programme was made confidentially available in January 2021, while the first round of webinars are organised in April-May 2021.																						

2.4 Business Support Programme for SMEs

Description	<p>The main goal of the Business Support Programme is to create a portfolio of business support services, which will help improve the investment readiness of SMEs and help them gain necessary investments to cross the "valley of death". It is focused on supporting SMEs in understanding an investor's way of thinking, identifying and positioning the relevant KPIs and tractions figures, developing winning pitches and knowing how to approach investors and other funding bodies. It is organised in the form of online webinars (to provide valuable concepts/insights and information) and online workshops.</p> <p>The specific topics to be covered under the BSP are:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="359 604 1420 1344"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="359 604 1236 683">Training topic and description</th> <th data-bbox="1236 604 1420 683">Partner responsible</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 683 1236 716">Project lifecycle and specific financing tasks and financing gaps</td> <td data-bbox="1236 683 1420 716">FSH</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 716 1236 750">Reporting and Exit strategies - life with an investor</td> <td data-bbox="1236 716 1420 750">CTA</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 750 1236 817">The process and phases of raising capital - main steps including legal specifications</td> <td data-bbox="1236 750 1420 817">CTA</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 817 1236 851">Market validation, evaluating the target market</td> <td data-bbox="1236 817 1420 851">SIE</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 851 1236 918">Financial Planning and how to extent your runway through access to finance</td> <td data-bbox="1236 851 1420 918">FBCD</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 918 1236 985">IPR Protection for bio-based SMEs: limitations, challenges, and common mistakes</td> <td data-bbox="1236 918 1420 985">Q-PLAN</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 985 1236 1019">Traction and valorisation</td> <td data-bbox="1236 985 1420 1019">TTG</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1019 1236 1052">The Important Role of a Strong and Complementary Team</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1019 1420 1052">FBCD</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1052 1236 1086">Customer needs</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1052 1420 1086">FSH</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1086 1236 1120">Competitor analysis</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1086 1420 1120">SIE</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1120 1236 1187">How to strategically match your company growth and EU funding opportunities</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1120 1420 1187">IBF</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1187 1236 1220">Crowdfunding Guide</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1187 1420 1220">FSH</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1220 1236 1254">How to create and deliver a compelling investor pitch deck</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1220 1420 1254">FSH</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1254 1236 1288">Sales and marketing channels</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1254 1420 1288">SIE</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="359 1288 1236 1332">PR & for SMEs/ scale-ups with case studies</td> <td data-bbox="1236 1288 1420 1332">FSH</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Training topic and description	Partner responsible	Project lifecycle and specific financing tasks and financing gaps	FSH	Reporting and Exit strategies - life with an investor	CTA	The process and phases of raising capital - main steps including legal specifications	CTA	Market validation, evaluating the target market	SIE	Financial Planning and how to extent your runway through access to finance	FBCD	IPR Protection for bio-based SMEs: limitations, challenges, and common mistakes	Q-PLAN	Traction and valorisation	TTG	The Important Role of a Strong and Complementary Team	FBCD	Customer needs	FSH	Competitor analysis	SIE	How to strategically match your company growth and EU funding opportunities	IBF	Crowdfunding Guide	FSH	How to create and deliver a compelling investor pitch deck	FSH	Sales and marketing channels	SIE	PR & for SMEs/ scale-ups with case studies	FSH
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Task(s)	T1.4, T4.3																																
Linked deliverables	D1.4, D4.3, D4.8																																
Partner(s) responsible	FSH was responsible for the overall design, set up and supervision of the BSP, while all project partners contributed to the effort and are responsible to deliver the Programme topics (see the table above).																																
Exploitation potential	<p>The Business Support Programme will provide a high-quality learning experience for all participating SMEs, allowing them to improve their investment readiness and ultimately secure investments, therefore gradually changing the European bioeconomy landscape.</p> <p>The different training materials (recordings of live webinars, presentations, additional material) will be available on the MPowerBIO e-learning platform (https://mpowerbio.eu/) to all participating SMEs as a guide and/or reference point.</p>																																
Availability	The first version of the MPowerBIO Business Support Programme was made confidentially available in January 2021, while the final programme is rolled out in May-July 2021.																																

2.5 MPowerBIO online platform

Description	<p>The MPowerBio Platform is central to achieving the expected impact of the project and incorporates digital tools that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • facilitate and collect SME profiles, support and assess their investment readiness level and define a business support roadmap customised for their needs. • empower SME clusters, industry experts and coaches to better support their SMEs and improve their investor readiness. <p>These objectives of the MPowerBio Platform are met by the following main features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital tools that allow SME clusters to perform an analysis of the investment readiness level of SMEs/projects and identify their strengths and weaknesses with a view to recommend a tailor-made service programme that addresses the needs and challenges; • An e-learning tool based on an open source Moodle platform, that will host all the online courses developed by MPowerBio and will be used by SME clusters and SMEs for their capacity building and training.
Task(s)	T2.1, T2.2
Linked deliverables	D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4
Partner(s) responsible	TTG is responsible for the development and operation of the platform.
Exploitation potential	The platform will be used during the two implementation cycles of the MPowerBIO Programmes, dispensing services and e-learning material that can constitute a reference point for any future activities of this kind.
Availability	The first version of the MPowerBIO Platform was made available in January 2021. The platform will be maintained and finetuned throughout the duration of the project.

2.6 Wider network of synergies

Description	<p>Throughout the implementation of the project, partners will coordinate, develop and benefit from synergies with other relevant clusters, initiatives and financial instruments at the national and European levels, with a particular focus on projects funded under the corresponding BBI value chain, other CSAs, H2020-INNOSUP call funded projects and COSME projects – the latter two involving SMEs and clusters.</p>
Task(s)	T3.1., T3.3
Linked deliverables	D3.1, D3.2, D3.4
Partner(s) responsible	CTA is responsible for engaging additional associated SME clusters across Europe and involving their networks, while IBF is in charge of promoting synergies and relations with other initiatives and financial instruments. All partners will

	contribute to this endeavour through their expertise and extensive contact networks.
Exploitation potential	This wider network of synergies will help foster and establish a new cooperation mentality, thus better promoting and contributing to the increased visibility of common objectives.
Availability	The first report on associated clusters engagement will be submitted in October 2021, while an updated version is expected in October 2022.

2.7 Trained corps of qualified cluster managers

Description	The deployment of the dedicated Capacity Building Programme in two iteration cycles, along with the several engagement activities foreseen to attract the highest possible number of clusters to benefit from MPowerBIO services are expected to occasion the creation of a pool of qualified cluster trainers, who will be able to confidently and effectively guide their SME members through the investment landscape quagmires, helping them design scalable and investment-ready projects.
Task(s)	T3.2
Linked deliverables	D3.3, D3.4
Partner(s) responsible	All partners will contribute to this endeavour through their expertise and extensive contact networks.
Exploitation potential	This trained corps of qualified cluster managers will be in a position to help their associated SMEs overcome the common financial hurdles that hinder their progress and commercialisation of their products
Availability	The first round of the Capacity Building Programme will be completed in May 2021.

2.8 Networks of investors

Description	Within the scope of its regional and pan-European competitions that bring together selected SMEs, clusters, investors, as well as industry and innovation experts, MPowerBIO will proceed to a general mobilisation of investors (Business Angels, Venture Capitals, Banks, Corporate Investors, institutional investors, EU/national/regional financial instrument representatives, etc.) that will lead to the setting up of relevant networks.
Task(s)	T5.2
Linked deliverables	D5.3, D5.4
Partner(s) responsible	TTG will lead the partners' effort to engage investors in the project activities. All partners will contribute to this endeavour through their expertise and extensive contact networks.

<p>Exploitation potential</p>	<p>Having been acquainted with the wider bioeconomy sector through previous participation in MPowerBIO competitions, a positive and fruitful experience, these investor networks could be called upon for any future similar activities and provide useful feedback and insights for potential business undertakings. Coming together and getting to know the bioeconomy sector and its stakeholders could help create open communication channels.</p>
<p>Availability</p>	<p>The network is already created but the effort to increase the number of investors will continue throughout the project duration.</p>

3. Knowledge management considerations

According to the Consortium Agreement signed by partners, the “*results are owned by the Party that generates them*” (Article 8.1 – Ownership of results) and, in general, joint property will arise when more than one partner contribute to generate that specific result (Article 8.2 – Joint ownership).

Considering the strong synergy, collaboration attitude and harmony within the MPowerBIO consortium, all partners will actively contribute to the realisation of each asset. Indeed, activities under each Work Package are led by the partner responsible for establishing the framework conditions and work distribution among the project partners (e.g. the task leader or organisation in charge of a specific deliverable), who are asked accordingly to provide their contribution.

According to this, all partners have a joint ownership of MPowerBIO assets and the IPRs are regulated by the Article 8.2 – Joint ownership of the Consortium Agreement, that says:

Results arising from joint work (from more than one Parties) under the Project shall be the joint property of the respective Parties. Unless otherwise agreed:

- *each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s), and*
- *each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given:*
 - a) *At least 45 calendar days advance notice; and*
 - b) *Fair and Reasonable compensation.*
- The joint owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related cost in advance

Important note: *the aforementioned provisions for the potential exploitation of each project asset will be updated (and if necessary revised) throughout the project implementation and will be detailed in the final version of this report.*